

A stress analysis with the finite element method of a tibia model with a bone callus

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Abstract

Human tibial fractures are complex injuries that usually result in long periods of hospitalization and rehabilitation. During the slow healing process, the bone callus gradually increases its mechanical properties. The aim of this work is to evaluate the structural influence of the gradual mechanical properties of a callus bone due to a transverse tibial fracture. Thus, a 2D tibia model was constructed and analysed using the finite element method (FEM). At the transverse fracture site, a bone callus was considered. In order to simulate the healing process, four distinct Young's moduli were assumed for the bone callus, ranging between the soft callus (250 MPa) and hard callus (6000 MPa) stages. All materials were assumed homogeneous, isotropic, and linear elastic. Distinct geometries and load cases were considered, simulating a normal alignment and malalignment conditions, such as a valgus and a varus knee. Each model was analysed with FEM assuming an elasto-static analysis and using constant strain triangular elements. Von Mises effective stress and principal stress fields were obtained for each model. The obtained results show that, compared to the aligned condition, both malalignment conditions induce the highest stress levels in the model. The maximum stresses were observed in the tibia model with the 250 MPa callus and gradually decreased with the increase of the mechanical properties of the callus.

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1 Introduction

The skeletal system is formed by living tissues that support the other tissues of the human body, however its integrity can be compromised when fractures occur. The prediction of fracture healing remains one of the major challenges [1]. Among long bones, tibial fractures are the most common fractures and usually result in long periods of hospitalization and rehabilitation [2]. The conventional method of assessing fracture healing in long bones is by a combination of passive manipulation of the injured limb, to assess the strength of the fracture, along with medical imaging to determine the volume and state of fracture-binding tissues, referred to as callus. However, this assessment method is subjective and unanimity lacks among clinicians [3]. Even though there is no consensus when a fracture is consolidated, clinical studies and individual patient assessment require a measurable definition that indicates the end of the consolidation. Thus, in research environment, there has been a need for objective, quantitative and simulation methods that allow monitoring the consolidation of the fracture, assisting the diagnosis and treatment of delayed unions and non-unions, as well as helping to identify the endpoint of healing, avoiding prolonged treatments.

One of the most notable features of living tissue is its ability to self-regenerate [4]. The healing process strongly depends on the mechanical actions on the callus, which determine the relative movement of the bone fragments. It is a complex process involving cellular differentiation, strongly stimulated by mechanical loading [4]. Knowledge of the mechanisms involved and their interdependencies with external factors supports the understanding of the accelerated regeneration processes and the success of rehabilitation [4]. The fractured bone is immobilized using a specific method to repair and restore its main function. In this process, the bone goes through four main phases: inflammation, soft callus formation, hard callus formation and bone remodelling. The healing process can be influenced by certain factors that can be divided in two categories: systemic factors such as age, pathologies or external factors, and local factors such as the degree of fracture, type of bone, blood supply, degree of vascularity and mechanical factors [4].

Mechanical stress or strain in fracture sites are typically estimated using finite element analysis (FEA). The Finite Element Method (FEM) is the most frequently used numeric tool for the analysis of bone architectures in structural mechanics. When a structure is loaded, stresses are generated in its constituent materials, characterized by their

magnitude and orientation, and by their distribution along the structure volume [5]. Those attributes depend not only on the constituent materials' properties and their spatial and geometric organization, but also on the intensity and position of the applied loads, and the system's boundary conditions [5]. Each element is associated with a material and a geometric shape, which define its stiffness. By assembling the stiffness matrix of all elements, it is possible to construct the global stiffness matrix of the model, $\mathbf{K}$, in which are imposed the essential boundary conditions. The natural boundary conditions (external forces), $\mathbf{F}$, are defined and the system of equations is established: $\mathbf{KU} = \mathbf{F}$, which allows to determine the displacement field, $\mathbf{U}$. FEM allows the division of a complex problem by discretizing the global structure into several simpler polygonal elements. The FEM is a useful tool to assess mechanical stimuli within healing fractures that cannot be measured directly during experimental investigations. Therefore, to simulate the consolidation process, the mechanical properties of the callus in its different phases must be known and reproduced. Although there are many studies in the literature on sheep and rat bone healing [6,7], some data can be found on callus stiffness in humans, as observed in Nikiforidis et al. [8] and Claes and Cunningham [9]. The approximate values of the Young's modulus of tissues can be found in numerical studies on bone consolidation simulation, in Milan et al. [10], Byrne et al. [11], Lacroix et al. [12] and Mehboob et al. [13]. In another study, some materials were used to simulate the consolidation phases [14].

This work aims to study how the variation of the Young's modulus of the bone callus (due to a transverse tibial fracture) influences the stress field in the healing fracture vicinity. Thus, the mechanical response of the tibia model, with a callus possessing distinct mechanical properties, is analysed using the finite element method. Furthermore, it is investigated how the geometry of the tibia, combined with the presence of a bone callus, influences the stress magnitude and distribution. Therefore, three models of the tibia were constructed, each one possessing its own load case: a normal tibia showing a normal alignment and two malalignment conditions, such as a valgus and a varus knee.

2 Materials and Methods

Three 2D models of the tibia bone were constructed in FEMAP© software (student version). The 2D models were obtained from anonymized radiographs of an adult male healthy individual, an adult male individual possessing the valgus malalignment condition and an adult male individual possessing the varus malalignment condition. All the models represent a left tibia model. A knee that is perfectly aligned has its load-bearing axis on a line that runs down the middle of the leg, through the hip, knee, and ankle. If the knee is not perfectly aligned, it is described as either valgus (knock-kneed), if the distal part is more lateral, or varus (bowlegged), if the distal part is more medial.

The three 2D models possess the same number of nodes and elements: 2461 nodes and 4574 triangular elements (constant strain elements). After the construction of the models, the corresponding node/element mesh was imported to the "Finite Element and Meshless Methods Analysis Software", FEMAS©, an academic freeware using MATLAB© environment (cmech.webs.com). All the models possess at the middle of the tibial diaphysis a transverse fracture, which was filled with callus material. The material properties and the essential and natural boundary conditions are inserted in FEMAS. The model is composed of two distinct materials: the homogeneous bone tissue and the callus. In this work, the homogenized bone tissue assumed the mechanical properties of a cortical bone. The mechanical properties of each one of the materials are represented in Table 1, in which it is possible to visualize the four different Young's moduli that were considered for the callus. The intention is to have the representative behaviour of each healing stage, in a range of elasticity values that vary between the soft callus, until a phase that represents the hard callus stage. Both Young's modulus (E) and Poisson's coefficient (ν) were obtained from the literature. All materials were assumed to be homogeneous, isotropic, and linear elastic.

Table 1 - Mechanical properties of the materials [12].

Material	Young's modulus (MPa)	Poisson's coefficient
Homogenized Bone Tissue	16700	0.3
Callus 1 (Cartilage)	250	0.4999
Callus 2 (Intermediate bone)	1500	0.4999
Callus 3 (Mature bone)	4000	0.4999
Callus 4 (Mature bone)	6000	0.4999

Regarding the essential boundary conditions (displacements constrains), the model was fixed in the distal extremity, with no displacement allowed in any of the directions of the two degrees-of-freedom. Concerning the natural boundary conditions (external forces), this work intends to analyse a peak load during walking for an approximately 80kg human being. Thus, assuming that the individual is standing in one leg, all the load is applied to the proximal tibia distributed

into a $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ surface. For the 2D analysis, is was considered the plane strain deformation theory. Thus, only a 2D slice with 1mm thickness was analysed. The load on that 1mm thickness was distributed at the proximal tibia (thus, only 1/10 of the total load). In this work, three 2D models were constructed, each one representing a health condition: normal alignment (case 1), 10° valgus malalignment (case 2) and 10° varus malalignment (case 3). Each one of these models will possess its own load. Therefore, for the normal alignment (case 1) it was considered: $\vec{F}_1 = \{0,80\}^T N$, for 10° valgus malalignment (case 2) it was assumed: $\vec{F}_2 = \{13.89, -78.78\}^T N$ and for 10° varus malalignment (case 3) it was considered: $\vec{F}_3 = \{-13.89, -78.78\}^T N$.

3 Numerical Results

The models described previously were analysed with FEM and the stress fields of the von Mises effective stress, σ_{ef} , and the principal stresses, σ_1 and σ_2 , were calculated. In Fig.1, for each bone callus and each geometric model, the obtained stress distribution maps are shown.

Fig.1 – Stress maps obtained with each model case: von Mises effective stresses (σ_{ef}) and principal stresses (σ_1 and σ_2) for each callus.

Fig.2 shows the average stress at the bone callus. The average stresses were obtained with: $\bar{\sigma} = n^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i$, being n the number of elements belonging to the bone callus area and σ_i the stress on element i (belonging to the bone callus). In

Fig.3, the stress variation along two region lines (region 1 represent the lateral zone of the diaphysis and region 2 represents the medial zone of the diaphysis) is shown for each bone callus and each geometric model.

Fig.2 – Average values at the callus' region for each case: von Mises effective stress σ_{ef} (a), principal stress σ_1 (b), principal stress σ_2 (c).

4 Discussion

In this work, the main goal was to understand the mechanical behaviour of the tibia with a callus of different mechanical properties that simulate the healing process. Furthermore, the influence of the geometry was also investigated, by analysing models presenting normal alignment and malalignment conditions, such as a valgus and a varus knee. Twelve models were constructed and analysed with FEM (three distinct geometries in which the Young's modulus of the bone callus was varied four times between 250MPa and 6000MPa). The FEM allowed to obtain the stress fields of each model, corresponding to the von Mises effective stress, σ_{ef} , and the principal stresses, σ_1 and σ_2 . The von Mises stress is a yield criterion that evaluates the maximum distortion energy of a material: a material starts to fail when the von Mises stress value approaches the material characteristic yield strength [15]. In the colour maps of Fig.1, the highest von Mises stresses are concentrated in different regions, being the highest values found at the tibial diaphysis. Considering Fig.2(a) and focusing only in the callus' region, the maximum average von Mises stresses were observed in the tibia model with the 250 MPa callus and then, it gradually decreased with the increase of the bone callus Young's modulus. This observation is valid for three 2D models analysed. Fig.2 shows that the both valgus knee (case 2) and varus knee (case 3) present very close average stresses. With Fig.2 it is possible to understand that the malalignment conditions (case 2 and case 3) induce stresses 350%–400% higher than a normal alignment condition. Thus, it is expected that malalignment conditions require larger immobilization periods when compared with a normal alignment condition (higher stresses at the bone callus can induce further damage and re-inflammation). The same observations can be made when the principal stresses σ_1 and σ_2 are analysed. In a 2D model, the highest positive values of σ_1 represent the highest tensile stress and the highest negative value (absolute value) of σ_2 represent the highest compressive stress. Fig.1 shows that the valgus knee (case 2) induces higher tensile stresses at the medial line of the diaphysis and higher compressive stresses at the lateral line of the diaphysis. On the other hand, the varus knee (case 3) induces higher tensile stresses at the lateral line of the diaphysis and higher compressive stresses at the medial line of the diaphysis.

Fig.3 allows to visualize the stress distribution with detail in both lateral diaphysis line (region 1) and medial diaphysis line (region 2). Thus, considering the diaphysis regions of the tibia, the lateral line (region 1) presents higher stress in each of the load cases compared to the medial line (region 2). Thus, in the lateral region, case 1 (Fig.3), the maximum von Mises effective stress was 6.07 MPa, the principal stress σ_1 was 0.3 MPa (absolute) and principal stress σ_2 was 6.48 MPa (absolute). These values are observed near the distal extremity of the tibia, for all the models of the tibia with callus' Young's modulus from 250 to 6000 MPa. On the other hand, in case 2 (Fig.3), von Mises' maximum stress was higher in the callus region, particularly in the model with the callus possessing a Young's modulus of 250 MPa, with a peak of 29.92 MPa, as well as for the principal stress σ_2 of 31.46 MPa (absolute). Near the distal extremity of the tibia, a second peak was observed for von Mises' stress, σ_{ef} =29.62 MPa, and for the principal stress σ_2 =30.41 MPa (absolute). For case 3 (Fig.3), the maximum peak is observed at the callus region, in which von Mises' stress reaches 19.54 MPa, principal stress σ_1 reaches 20.47 MPa and principal stress σ_2 achieves 2.02 MPa. These highest values are obtained for bone callus with a Young's modulus of 250 MPa.

Fig.3 – Values of the von Mises effective stress σ_{ef} , principal stress σ_1 and principal stress σ_2 , for each model case, at region lines.

Subsequently, for the medial region, case 1 (Fig.3), the maximum von Mises effective stress was 3.13 MPa, for all the models of the tibia regardless the Young's modulus of the callus bone, in the callus region. For the case 2 (Fig.3), the maximum von Mises effective stress was 23.33 MPa and maximum principal stress σ_1 of 23.71 MPa, near the distal extremity of the tibia, for all the models of the tibia with callus. In the callus region, it was observed a maximum von

Mises stress of 22.63 MPa and principal stress σ_1 of 23.77 MPa, for the model with the callus' Young's modulus of 250 MPa. Lastly, in case 3 (Fig.3), the maximum stresses are obtained for the bone callus possessing a Young's modulus of 250 MPa. Thus, a maximum von Mises' stress of 27.63 MPa is observed and a principal stress σ_1 of 3.22 MPa (absolute) and principal stress σ_2 of 29.1 MPa (absolute).

5 Conclusions

Tibia is one of the most important long bone and the main weight-bearing bone of the human leg, being responsible for receiving the body weight and transmit it to the foot when a human being stands or walks. A 2D simulation was performed aiming to obtain the stress distribution in the tibia. In order to perform the computational simulation, several approximations were assumed to simplify the model, e.g. the bone was considered isotropic and the FEM analysis was performed assuming the 2D plane strain deformation theory (2D-PSDT). These simplifications only allow to approximate the solution. Nevertheless, since 2D-PSDT is a simplification of the full 3D deformation theory for a target observation plane, it is expected that the obtained 2D stress distributions are very close with the real 3D stress distributions in the observed plane. Thus, the obtained results allow to understand the stress distribution in the tibia bone and predict which locations are under higher stress levels. This work also shows how a material discontinuity, such as a bone callus, influences the stress distribution, as well as variations in the geometry of the tibia bone and in the material properties of the callus bone.

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